

JACEK HILSZCZAŃSKI¹

Afromegischus gigas (SCHLETTERER, 1889) a new species
of the family Stephanidae (Hymenoptera)
for continental Europe

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14824938>

¹ Department of Forest Protection, Forest Research Institute, Śękocin Stary, Braci Leśnej 3,
05-090 Raszyn, Poland, e-mail: hilszczj@ibles.waw.pl, ORCID: 0000-0002-4731-0044

² Anogia 9, 23054 Sparta, Laconia Peloponnese Greece, e-mail: iwonaborek@interia.eu

³ e-mail: tarwackg@ibles.waw.pl, ORCID: 0000-0001-5979-7788

Abstract: *Afromegischus gigas* is recorded for the first time from Greece (Peloponnese) as new for continental Europe, what suggest that the species is probably spreading along with the changing climate.

Key words: Hymenoptera, Stephanidae, faunistic, new records, Greece, Peloponnese.

INTRODUCTION

Stephanidae is a small, cosmopolitan family found mainly in tropical and subtropical forest ecosystems. In the Palearctic, this family is known mainly from the southern part of the region and the same is true for Europe, where 4 species have been found so far. Two of them, i.e. *Stephanus serrator* (FABRICIUS, 1798) and *Megischus anomalipes* (FOERSTER, 1855) are widespread, mainly in the Mediterranean region, and the other two, i.e. *Foenatopus turcomanorum* (SEMENOV, 1891) and *Afromegischus gigas* (SCHLETTERER, 1889) are known so far in Europe only from the island of Crete (HILSZCZAŃSKI 2011, CECCOLINI 2021). Stephanidae are rarely collected, which is probably due to their hidden way of life, which is concentrated on the breeding material of their hosts, i.e. wood infested by larvae of saproxylic insects. Stephanidae usually do not visit flowers, which makes it even more difficult to find them in the field.

METHODS AND RESULTS

In 2024, 2 females of *A. gigas* (Fig. 1) were collected while penetrating the cut branches of the downy oak *Quercus pubescens* WILLD., lying in a sunny place in the home garden. This is the first record of this spectacular parasitoid species in continental Europe. Evidence specimens are in the collection of the first author. The map was created using ArcMap 10.5 Software.

Greece: Peloponnese Laconia, Anogia, 27.VI.2024, 2 females leg. Robert Borek

Fig. 1. Female of *Afromegischus gigas* (SCHLETTERER, 1889) from Peloponnese (Greece). A – habitus, dorsal view; B – head, dorsal view; C – head, front view; D – first segment of gaster and hind leg, dorsal view; E – fore wing (photos ???).

DISCUSSION

Afromegischus gigas is the largest European representative of the Stephanidae family, females together with the ovipositor reach a length of up to 60 mm. This species was described from Iran from the town of Shiraz in the province of Fars (SCHLETTERER 1889). Recently rediscovered in Iran at several other localities (MASNADI-YAZDINEJAD & LOTFALIZADEH 2009). In addition to Iran, the species has been found in Turkey, and in Europe so far the only place of occurrence was the Greek island of Crete (HILSZCZAŃSKI 2011) (Fig. 2).

Stephanidae represent an ecological group of idiobionts, ectoparasitoids and are associated with beetle larvae living in wood, especially the larvae of longhorn beetles Cerambycidae and jewel beetles Buprestidae, less often with larvae of Siricidae, which was found in the case of the genus *Schlettererius* belonging to these parasitoids (van ACHTERBERG 2002). Little is known about the host associations of *A. gigas*. In Iran, 3 females and a male were reared from

Fig. 2. Distribution of known localities of *A. gigas*. Iran: 1 – Tehran, 2 – Yazd (MASNADI-YAZDINEJAD & LOTFALIZADEH 2009), 3 – Shiraz (SCHLETTERER 1889); Turkey: 4 – Gülнар (HILSZCZAŃSKI 2011); Greece, Krete: 5 – Azogyres (HILSZCZAŃSKI 2011); Greece: 6 – Anogia, new locality.

wood infested by the powder beetle *Bostrychus capuicinus* (L.) (Coleoptera: Bostrychidae) (MASNADI-YAZDINEJAD & LOTFALIZADEH 2009). However, given the size, especially of the female parasitoid, it may be doubtful whether the larvae of this beetle are indeed hosts of *A. gigas*. This parasitoid was bred from Crete from dead branches of the plane tree *Platanus* sp. colonized by the larvae of the buprestid *Strigopterooides margotanae* NOVAK (HILSZCZAŃSKI 2011) and in this case a host relationship is more likely. It must be assumed that the downy oak branches on which *A. gigas* was caught in Greece would also be infested by larvae of saproxylic beetles.

Despite the small number of specialists identifying parasitoids of the family Stephanidae, it seems unlikely that an insect of the size of *A. gigas* could be overlooked in the fauna of Greece. It can be assumed that this species is spreading, inhabiting new areas with an increasingly favorable climate, and at the same time abundant in breeding material inhabited by host larvae. It is expected that with climate change, other species of the Stephanidae family currently found south of Europe will also be found on this continent.

REFERENCES

- CECCOLINI F. 2021. New records for crown wasps in Europe (Hymenoptera, Stephanidae). *Arxius de Miscellània Zoològica* 19: 249–259.
- HILSZCZAŃSKI J. 2011. New data on the occurrence of stephanids (Hymenoptera, Stephanidae) in Turkey and Greece. *Nature Journal* 44: 192–196.
- MASNADI-YAZDINEJAD A., LOTFALIZADEH H. 2009. Rediscovery of *Afromegischus gigas* (SCHLETTERER, 1889) (Hymenoptera, Stephanidae) from Iran. *North-Western Journal of Zoology* 5(1): 8–15.
- SCHLETTERER A. 1889. Monographie der Hymenopteren-Gattung *Stephanus* JUR. *Berliner Entomologische Zeitschrift* 33: 71–160.
- van ACHTERBERG C. 2002. A revision of the Old World species of *Megischus* BRULLÉ, *Stephanus* JURINE and *Pseudomegischus* gen. nov., with a key to the genera of the family Stephanidae (Hymenoptera: Stephanoidea). *Zoologische Verhandelingen Leiden* 339: 1–206.

Accepted: 16 January 2025; published: 6 February 2025

Licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution License <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>